

PROCESS AND CRITERIA OF TEACHING LISTENING

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Annotation

The purpose of this work is to study methods of teaching the listening to young learners in context traditions. The work is devoted to the study of modernizing and modeling English listening materials and usage of modern techniques.

Index Terms – language, listening, teaching listening, comprehension, communication, social-cognitive model, sociolinguistic paradigm, button-up, top-down, gist activity, dictation, education.

INTRODUCTION

At present, a very urgent problem is consideration of the methods of teaching foreign languages, in particular, English, as well as the main trends in its development.

Shavkat Miramanovich Mirziyoyev noted that "science, education, upbringing are the cornerstone of development, the force that increases the power of the country and people. Tomorrow, the future of the Motherland is inextricably linked with the education system and the upbringing that our children receive today."

Course work provides an opportunity to get acquainted with the methods of

teaching listening to younger students. It also provides an opportunity to familiarize with the lesson plan where an exercise is provided to improve the quality of listening skills.

II BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

Most people believe that knowing a second language entails being able to speak and write in that language. As a result, listening and reading are considered secondary skills - tools for achieving other goals rather than goals in and of themselves.

"Listening, on the other hand, comes into fashion now and then. The emphasis on spoken language abilities in the 1960s gave it a boost. It was popular again in the 1980s," according to Krashen's thoughts regarding [1].

In the 1970s and 1980s, the definition of listening came to be accepted as evaluating the cultural relevance of speech behavior. The primary theoretical paradigms of learning and understanding were interactionist and sociolinguistic movements [4]. In the field of hearing, the educational focus was on practicing listening skills based on socially and contextually appropriate responses to spoken texts. At the time, the input instruments were actual recordings, face-to-face learner conversation, and expert speaker-learner interaction [4]. Scholars such as Rubin and Stern proposed in 1975 that some decent language learners might be employing tactics to acquire a second or foreign language, rather than merely having an ear or innate capacity for language learning.

Listening became popular in the 1990s. At that time, Krashen's [1] views on understandable input (which were later represented in Asher's [2] entire bodily reaction) gained traction. Furthermore, with the introduction of communicative language teaching (CLT) methodologies and a focus on listening as a common modality of human communication, a strong need for language listening skills was realized. The use of listening tactics for improving comprehension and coping with challenges became fashionable with the introduction of social-

cognitive models of comprehension, as well as the existing inter-actionist and sociolinguistic paradigms of comprehension.

Since the 1990s afterward, some models have been presented to describe the nature of listening comprehension. The theoretical foundations are presented in the following entries.

III METHODOLOGY

Theoretical and practical methods of research are used in given course paper, such as publishing analysis, prediction of the acquired. The language description is an assessment of each language level and its parts for educational purposes, linguistic operations to determine the content and structure of the relevant section of a language learning course, language forms for books, books and dictionaries, 'reef and description.

Minimum theoretical knowledge for students. Bilingual language description for learning purposes focuses on exploring the similarities and differences between different levels of language and identifying the role of language in different bilingual contexts.

IV DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Principals of teaching listening

1) Introduce kids to different styles of information processing: bottom-up vs. top-down.

Rumelhart and Ortony (1977) “presented bottom-up vs. top-down information processing, which was developed up **Ошибка! Источник ссылки не найден.** by Chaudron and Richards (1986)”[10], Richards (1990), and others. The distinction is made based on how students try to comprehend what they read or hear. When students use bottom-up processing, they start with the basics: vocabulary, grammar, and so on. The opposite of bottom-up processing is top-down processing. Learners begin with their prior knowledge, either content schema (general information based on past learning and life experience) or textual schema (textual information based on previous learning and life experience)

(awareness of the kinds of information used in a given situation)[8]. Interactive processing is also available. The utilization of a top-down and bottom-up approach processing is called interactive process.

2) Introduce kids to several styles of listening

Any discussion of listening tasks must include a discussion of listening styles. Tasks and text should both be considered in this case. When talking about hearing, the term "text" refers to whatever the students are listening to, which is usually a recording. Listening for specific information is the most common type of listening exercise found in many textbooks. This usually entails gathering specific information such as names, dates, and times.

At other times, students attempt to comprehend in a broader sense. This is referred to as "global" or "gist" listening. Identifying important ideas, marking a sequence of events, and other similar tasks are common in the classroom. These two modes of listening, on the other hand, do not exist in isolation. Another example is inference. This is "listening between the lines"- that is, listening for meaning that is implied not stated directly. It is a higher level skill.

3) Teach a variety of skills.

Listening students must complete a range of exercises. Because learners do the job while listening, it is critical that the assignment does not require excessive production from the learner. If a beginner level student hears a tale and is requested to write a summary in English, it's possible that the learner comprehended the story but isn't yet at the level to write the synopsis. It's also possible that they don't answer despite knowing what you're saying. It's possible they understood at the moment but forgot when it came time to do the task. This is an example of If you're doing a summary task based on a tale, it could be better to create a task where you have to choose the best summary from two or three options.

4) Think about the text, the difficulty, and the sincerity.

Written and spoken languages are vastly different. It's clumsier, with more false

beginnings, rephrasing, and elaborations. There are a lot of incomplete sentences, pauses, and overlaps. Natural-sounding language must be exposed to and practiced by students.

When students discuss text difficulty, the first thing they usually notice is speed, which can be an issue. But the solution isn't to make them listen to recordings that are excessively slow and clear. These can truly alter the sound of the language. However, speed isn't the only factor to consider. Brown (1995) outlines “six characteristics that increase or decrease the ease of understanding as cognitive load.”

V RESULTS

Classroom approaches that to intend to use in the classroom

Dictation with a twist

For many teachers, listening for precise information is synonymous with dictation. Dictation, as it is commonly used, has several drawbacks because it is purely bottom-up, requiring students to capture every word. As a result, dictation frequently requires students to do tasks in a foreign language that are unnatural and difficult even in their own tongue. Another issue is that because dictation is a word-by-word exercise, students are not required to consider the entire meaning. As a result, appropriate exercises to address those issues should be identified.

Classroom approaches that I intend to use in the classroom are as follows:

Do-it-yourself: Adding "Listening for specific information" to materials

While the most prevalent sort of listening in textbooks is listening for particular, teachers may want to add their own activities. The methods listed below can be used to listen for specifics.

- Micro-listening
- Bits and pieces of information
- What do I want to know?
- Dictation and cloze

Adding gist activities

While many textbooks focus on listening for specific information, changing them into global listening tasks can often be as simple as asking "What are they talking about?" What were the words that offered you the clues? Here are a few more ways to incorporate gist listening.

- The most important concepts
- What is the sequence of events?
- Which image do you mean?

Between the lines listening: Tasks requiring inference:

Inference is as much a function of the text (what is said) as it is of the task. Teachers, on the other hand, should endeavor to be conscious of inference and look for ways to work with it. Here are two good places to start:

Focus on the speakers' emotions: how do they feel? How did you figure that out?

Investigate the following sources for background information: Is one or more of the speakers available?

Relationships that are simple are easier to comprehend than those that are complex.

The sequence of events; the quantity of inferences required; and the information's consistency with what the listener already knows.

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Any discussion of listening texts will very certainly have to address the question of authentic texts. No one can deny that the texts that students deal with should be realistic. Some argue, however, that all materials used by students should be genuine. However, the issue of authenticity is not as straightforward as it may appear. The majority of the recordings that come with textbooks are created in studios. And recordings done outside of a studio are frequently of poor quality.

In the process of research of course paper, the writer thoroughly studied what listening is and concluded that listening skill is a complex and diverse phenomenon. The professor must first grasp the challenges that their students confront in order to improve their listening skills.

Take into consideration, researcher sum up that learners should practice listening in a variety of contexts to help them develop both types of listening abilities and integrate them with some or all of the other skill categories.

In this research researcher represent information about methods and principles. Also, considered how listening as a separate subject developed. Who invested in its development, in what years the active development of methods for teaching listening began. By the end experimenter conclude that the tools used to practice listening in the classroom should be as natural as possible. It also raises the issue of using the teacher's own naturalness of speech with the students. When a student wants to listen to the news on the radio or make a phone call in English, slow, awkward speaking is not helpful.

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